

THE CONTENT EXPLANATION OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COMPETENCE IN SAFELY SEARCHING FOR INFORMATION IN ACADEMIC LYCEUMS

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Annotation. *This article presents and analyses the scientific views of scientists in the field on the specifics of safe information search by academic lyceum students, the scientific and theoretical justification of information forms and its development, the use and storage of information, and ensuring its security, and expresses a subjective attitude to them.*

Keywords: *academic lyceum students, information, information security, specificity of information search, information forms, scientific and theoretical justification, information use, subjective attitude.*

Today, it is desirable to radically improve the knowledge, skills and qualifications of academic lyceum students in working with and searching for information. In this regard, it is essential to develop in them the skills of information security and safe information search.

Therefore, one of the main tasks is to teach them the scientific and theoretical basis for ensuring information security.

“Information security is the practice of preventing unauthorized access, use, disclosure, alteration, modification, retrieval, recording, or destruction of information. This universal concept applies regardless of the form in which the information is stored (e.g., electronic or physical). The primary goal of information security is to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information in a manner that is balanced with the appropriateness of its use and without causing any harm to the organization’s operations. This is achieved primarily through a multi-stage risk management process that identifies fixed and intangible assets, threat sources, vulnerabilities, potential impacts, and existing risk management capabilities.

This process is carried out in conjunction with an assessment of the effectiveness of the risk management plan”¹. In academic lyceums, continuous training in students' knowledge of the balance between confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information in order to develop their competence in safe information search will increase their skills in working with information and the culture of information search.

In this regard, the approach of scientist O.G. Davlatov is worthy of praise. In his research on the topic "Developing students' information security competence through historical and cultural heritage": "An information attack or threat is a set of conditions and factors that pose a threat to the vital interests of an individual, society, and the state in the information sphere"², emphasizes.

We believe that it is necessary to treat information as a necessary heritage and develop a set of measures to ensure its security.

¹ https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Axborot_xavfsizligi

² Davlatov O.G'. Talabalarda axborot xavfsizligini ta'minlash kompetenstligini tarixiy-madaniy meros vositasida rivojlantirish. Ped.fan.fals.dok...diss. Toshkent-2018. -21 b.

A.B. Volodkin, A.L. Manoshkin in their book "Information Security"³ understand information security as the protection of information in an information computing system from accidental and intentional effects of an internal or external nature that can cause harm to information users and owners of information resources.

"A security policy is a set of standards, rules, and practical recommendations that govern the operation of protective measures given the risk of information security"⁴.

According to S.K. Ganiyev, M.M. Karimov, K.A. Tashayev, "Information security is characterized by the protection of information from inappropriate (for the relevant subjects of information relations) disclosure (violation of confidentiality), violation of its integrity, leakage, loss, modification or decrease in the level of usability, and illegal circulation. These events may be caused by accidental impacts or by deliberate unauthorized use by an attacker (with malicious intent)"⁵.

"Currently, information security assessment is one of the most relevant and dynamically developing areas of research. There are various methodologies for assessing risks, ranging from informal methods to the use of specialized software tools"⁶.

"Cybersecurity objectives do not rely directly on behavior, but a cybersecurity strategy based on cybersecurity objectives is expected to result in a better cybersecurity policy.

Organizations create standards for implementing technology controls and related operational processes, and components use these standards to ensure compliance with the policy. Standards are not policies themselves. Rather, they are a reference to a set of technologies and operational processes for policy purposes. If a standard is aimed at policy compliance, it specifies a combination of process and technology configurations that will ensure policy compliance"⁷.

"Another educational object in teaching information security and cybersecurity is the textbook "Fundamentals of Information Security" compiled by B. Tahirov"⁸. This textbook covers the content of the science of information systems security, the subject of information security, the essence of auditing, its goals and objectives, the main concepts of ensuring information security, threats, protection methods, stages of cybersecurity and protection against cyberattacks, analysis of related concepts and explanations of terms, topics and theoretical information on the main software and technical tools for ensuring information security, scientific views of industry experts, analytical approaches, and research conclusions. In academic lyceums, in developing students' competence in safe information search, understanding the content of information system security, its true essence in terms of search, goals and objectives, concepts and threats is characterized as the main criterion for search.

³ Володкин А.Б., Маношкин А.Л. Информационная безопасность М. НТЦ. "ФИОРД-ИНФО" 2002 г.

⁴ Шаньгин, В. Ф. Информационная безопасность компьютерных систем и сетей : учеб. пособие / В.Ф. Шаньгин. — Москва : ИД «ФОРУМ» : ИНФРА-М, 2018. — 416 с

⁵ G'aniyev S.K., Karimov M.M., Tashayev K.A. Axborot xavfsizligi. Oliy o'quv yurt talabalari uchun mo'ljallangan o'quv qo'llanma. "Fan va texnologiya" nashriyoti, Toshkent -2016.

⁶ Баранова Э.К. Бабаш А.Б. Информационная безопасность и защита информации / - М.: ИНФРА-М -РИОР, 2014 г., 216 с.

⁷ Radjabova M.Sh. Kiberxavfsizlik siyosati haqida umumiy ma'lumotlar O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali 18-SON 20.04.2023.-885b

⁸ Tahirov B.N. Axborot xavfsizligi asoslari [Matn] : o'quv qo'llanma / B.N. Tahirov - Buxoro: Fan va ta'lim, 2022.-156 b.

Therefore, in the practical implementation of the strategic goals of developing students' competence in safe information search in academic lyceums, it is important to acquire knowledge on storing information, summarizing it, and appropriately applying it in life, as well as teaching them to work with Internet pages, a variety of information resources, and social networks that are free from various threats.

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